

Contribution to the Knowledge of the Fauna of the Alydidae, Anthocoridae, Berytidae, Coreidae, Cydnidae, Lygaeidae, Nabidae, Plataspidae, Pyrrhocoridae, Reduviidae, Rhopalidae, Scutelleridae, Stenocephalidae, Tingidae (Hemiptera: Heteroptera) with a new record of Çankırı Province in Türkiye

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ABSTRACT: This study was carried out in the Çankırı province between 2013 and 2014. In this study, 57 species from 14 families (Alydidae, Anthocoridae, Berytidae, Coreidae, Cydnidae, Lygaeidae, Nabidae, Plataspidae, Pyrrhocoridae, Reduviidae, Rhopalidae, Scutelleridae, Stenocephalidae, Tingidae) were recorded. Among them *Metopoplax ditomoides* (A. Costa) determined as new record for the fauna of Türkiye. Also, we confirm second record of *Legnotus picipes* (Fallén), previously given only from Erzurum in Türkiye.

KEYWORDS: Heteroptera, Fauna, New record, Çankırı, Türkiye.

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INTRODUCTION

The order Hemiptera Linnaeus, 1758 ranks fifth in the world with 104,165 species after the orders Coleoptera, Diptera, Lepidoptera and Hymenoptera (Zhang, 2011). Heteroptera Latreille, 1810 is a suborder of Hemiptera which contains 42,347 described species (Henry, 2009). The number of species listed from the Palaearctic Region increased from 8571 to 9365 in the period with the publication of the original six volumes (1995-2013) (Aukema & Rieger, 1995; 1996; 1999; 2001; 2006; 2013).

Türkiye has been known to possess a rich fauna of Heteroptera. Thus, many faunistic and systematic studies about the Heteroptera have been conducted by both foreign and native researchers in Türkiye. Some faunistic studies on this suborder in the Türkiye have been made by Horváth, 1901; Kiritschenko, 1918; Seidenstücker, 1954; Hoberlandt 1955; Linnavuori, 1965; Tuatay et al., 1972; Önder et al., 1984; Çakır & Önder, 1990; Kıyak et al., 2004; Önder et al., 2006; Dursun, 2009, 2011a, 2011b; Fent & Aktaç, 2009; Abacıgil et al., 2010; Dursun et al., 2010; Yıldırım et al., 2010, 2011, 2013a, 2013b, 2014a, 2014b; Fent & Japoshvili, 2012; Maral et al., 2013; Matocq et al., 2014; Küçükbasmacı & Kıyak, 2015; Dursun & Fent, 2009, 2015, 2017; Aysal & Kıvan, 2018; Çerçi et al., 2018; Yazıcı, 2019, 2022; Zengin & Dursun, 2019; Bolu, 2020; Akman & Dursun, 2021; Çerçi & Özgen, 2021; Kıyak & Baş, 2021; Yılmaz & Dursun, 2022; Fent & Dursun, 2022). In Türkiye, 1349 species from 469 genera from Heteroptera have been recorded so far. The type locality of 237 species are from Türkiye and 107 species and 4 subspecies are endemic to Türkiye (Dursun & Fent, 2017).

Studies on the Heteroptera in Türkiye, revealed are currently represented as Alydidae (8); Anthocoridae (41); Berytidae (24); Coreidae (50); Cydnidae (41); Lygaeidae (275); Nabidae (24); Plataspididae (7); Pyrrhocoridae (3); Reduviidae (65); Rhopalidae (30); Stenocephalidae (7) and Tingidae (89) Scutelleridae (40); (Tezcan, 2020).

Çankırı, which is the study province, is located between the Central Anatolian Geographical Region and the Black Sea Geographical Region, and therefore it contains the characteristics of both regions and constitutes a transition area. The lands of Çankırı Province are shared between the Western Black Sea Section of the Black Sea Region and the Central Kızılırmak Section of the Central Anatolia Region (Gökmen, 2007). Because of these features, it has a rich Heteroptera fauna. The aim of this study is to present new collection and biological data on Heteroptera in Çankırı. In this paper, 57 species of 43 genera belonging to 14 families from the suborder Heteroptera are recorded.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The Heteroptera materials were collected from different localities in Çankırı province 2013-2014. Samples were collected using traps and/or mouth aspirator. Collected samples were taken into pre-prepared kill bottles containing 70% alcohol and killed. The available specimens for the present study are deposited in Gazi University (Türkiye: Ankara).

RESULTS

In this study, 57 species of 43 genera belonging to 14 families from the suborder Heteroptera were recorded from Türkiye.

Family ALYDIDAE Amyot & Serville, 1843

Subfamily: Alydinae Amyot & Serville, 1843

Genus: *Alydus* Fabricius, 1803***Alydus calcaratus* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Cimex calcaratus Linnaeus, 1758; *Lygaeus tibialis* Fabricius, 1798; *Alydus hirsutus* Kolenati, 1845; *Alydus atratus* Motschulsky, 1860; *Alydus pluto* Uhler, 1872; *Alydus calcaratus* var. *ater* Jakovlev, 1876.

Material examined: Çankırı prov.: Çerkeş, between Yıprak-Tohumluk Villages, 40°55'1" N, 32°48'34"E, 1153 m 26.VIII.2013, 2 ♂♂; Çerkeş, Çakmak Village entrance, 40°58'16"N, 33°1'4" E, 1523 m 27.VIII.2013, ♂.

Previous records: Adana, Amasya, Ankara, Artvin, Balıkesir, Bayburt, Çankırı, Çorum, Erzurum, Giresun, İzmir, Kars, Kastamonu, Kayseri, Tokat, Trabzon (Önder et al., 2006; Dursun, 2009; Dursun et al., 2010; Yıldırım et al., 2011, 2013a; Fent & Japoshvili, 2012; Küçükbasmacı & Kıyak, 2015; Zengin & Dursun, 2019; Akman & Dursun, 2021; Kıyak & Baş, 2021).

Genus: *Camptopus* Amyot & Serville, 1843***Camptopus lateralis* (Germar, 1817)**

Alydus lateralis Germar, 1817; *Alydus annulatus* Brullé, 1832; *Alydus geranii* Dufour, 1833 *Alydus marginalis* Herrich-Schaeffer, 1835; *Alydus occipes* Herrich-Schaeffer, 1835; *Alydus brevipes* Herrich-Schaeffer, 1840; *Alydus undulatus* Westwood, 1842; *Camptopus lateralis* var. *obscurus* Reuter, 1890.

Material examined: Çankırı Prov.: Yapraklı, Söğütlü village, 40°40' 38" N, 33°57'41"E, 1376 m 24.VII.2013, ♀, ♂.

Previous records: Adıyaman, Ağrı, Amasya, Ankara, Antalya, Ardahan, Artvin, Balıkesir, Bayburt, Bingöl, Bolu, Çankırı, Çorum, Diyarbakır, Elazığ, Erzincan, Erzurum, Gaziantep, Giresun, Gümüşhane, Hatay, Iğdır, Isparta, İstanbul, Kars, Kastamonu, Kayseri, Konya, Malatya, Manisa, Mersin, Muğla, Muş, Nevşehir, Niğde, Sivas, Tokat, Tunceli, Van (Linnavuori, 1965; Lodos et al., 1984; Kıyak et al., 2004; Dursun, 2009; Dursun et al., 2010; Yıldırım et al., 2011, 2013a; Fent & Japoshvili, 2012; Matocq et al., 2014; Küçükbasmacı & Kıyak, 2015; Çerçi et al., 2018; Zengin & Dursun, 2019; Bolu, 2020; Akman & Dursun, 2021; Bulak & Yıldırım, 2021; Çerçi & Özgen, 2021; Kıyak & Baş, 2021).

Family ANTHOCORIDAE Fieber, 1836**Subfamily: Anthocorinae Fieber, 1836****Tribe: Anthocorini Fieber, 1836****Genus: *Anthocoris* Fallén*****Anthocoris nemoralis* (Fabricius, 1794)**

Acanthia nemoralis Fabricius, 1794; *Cimex triguttatus* Schrank, 1796; *Lygaeus austriacus* Fabricius, 1803; *Anthocoris nemoralis* var. *superbus* Westhoff, 1881; *Anthocoris dohrni* Le Quesne, 1958; *Anthocoris pemphigi* Wagner, 1960.

Material examined: Çankırı Prov.: Yapraklı, Yakadere village, 40°41'25"N, 33°48'56"E, 1030 m, 24.VII.2013, ♂; Bayramören, between Piriçli and Sazak Village, 40°58'20"N, 33°4'47"E, 1630 m, 27.VIII.2013, ♀.

Previous records: Ankara, Antalya, Bartın, Bolu, Erzincan, Erzurum, Kayseri, Mardin, Mersin (Hoberlandt, 1955; Linnavuori, 1965; Yıldırım et al., 2013b; Matocq et al., 2014; Yazıcı, 2019, 2022).

Family: BERYTIDAE Fieber, 1851**Subfamily: Berytinae Fieber, 1851****Tribe: Berytini Fieber, 1851**

Genus: *Berytinus* Kirkaldy, 1900***Berytinus (Berytinus) clavipes* (Fabricius, 1775)**

Cimex clavipes Fabricius, 1775; *Cimex suecicus* Gmelin, 1790; *Berytus caucasicus* Kolenati, 1845; *Berytus angustipennis* A. Costa, 1858; *Berytus vittatus* Fieber, 1859; *Berytus stettinensis* Dohrn, 1860; *Berytus (Xanthocerus) longicollis* Mulsant & Rey, 1870; *Berytinus longiceps* Wagner, 1966.

Material examined: Çankırı prov.: Kurşunlu, Çaylıca village exit, 40°54' 31" N, 33°14'52"E, 1316 m, 22.IV.2013, ♂.

Previous records: Diyarbakır (Lodos et al., 1984; Bolu, 2020).

Family: COREIDAE Leach, 1815**Subfamily: Coreinae Leach, 1815****Tribe: Coreini Leach, 1815****Genus: *Centrocoris* Kolenoti, 1845*****Centrocoris spiniger* (Fabricius, 1781)**

Cimex spiniger Fabricius, 1781; *Cimex branderi* Linnaeus, 1767; *Centrocoris pallescens* Kolenati, 1845; *Centrocoris spiniger* race *subinermis* Rey, 1887; *Centrocoris bampurensis* Linnavuori, 1968.

Material examined: Çankırı Prov.: Yapraklı, Söğütlü village, 40°40'38"N, 33°57'41"E, 1376 m, 24.VII.2013, ♀.

Previous records: Adana, Adıyaman, Amasya, Ankara, Antalya, Artvin, Balıkesir, Bursa, Çanakkale, Çorum, Diyarbakır, Edirne, Erzincan, Erzurum, Giresun, Hatay, Iğdır, Isparta, İstanbul, İzmir, Kars, Kayseri, Konya, Mardin, Mersin, Muğla Nevşehir, Sivas, Şanlıurfa, Tokat, Tunceli (Linnavuori, 1965; Kıyak et al., 2004; Önder et al., 2006; Dursun & Fent, 2009; Dursun, 2011b; Yıldırım et al., 2011, 2013a; Matocq et al., 2014; Zengin & Dursun, 2019; Bolu, 2020; Akman & Dursun, 2021; Kıyak & Baş, 2021).

Genus: *Coreus* Fabricius, 1794***Coreus marginatus* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Cimex marginatus Linnaeus, 1758; *Cimex auriculatus* De Geer, 1773; *Cimex rostratus* Goeze, 1778; *Copium serratum* Thunberg, 1825; *Coreus fundator* Herrich-Schaeffer, 1833; *Syromastes longicornis* A. Costa, 1842; *Coreus marginatus* var. *inermis* Kolenati, 1845; *Syromastes marginatus* var. *SYcus* Blöte, 1935.

Material examined: Çankırı Prov.: Eldivan, Eldivan entry, 40°32'25"N, 33°30'18"E, 922 m, 23.IV.2013, 3 ♀♀; Bayramören, between piriçli and Sazak village, 40°58'20"N, 33°4'47"E, 1630 m, 27.VIII.2013, ♀; Bayramören, Göynükören village, Hasanlar District, 41°0'55"N, 33°8'12"E, 1100 m, 27.VIII.2013, 2 ♀♀; Çerkeş, between Kadılar-Dikenli Plateau, 40°47'35"N, 32°44'35"E, 1449 m, 28.VIII.2013, ♀, 2 ♂♂; Çerkeş, between Dere and Suluk plateau, 40°42'44"N, 32°52'56"E, 1422 m, 29.VIII.2013, ♀.

Previous records: Adana, Ağrı, Amasya, Ankara, Antalya, Ardahan, Artvin, Aydın, Balıkesir, Bartın, Bayburt, Bilecik, Bingöl, Burdur, Bursa, Çanakkale, Çankırı, Çorum, Denizli, Edirne, Elazığ, Erzincan, Erzurum, Gaziantep, Giresun, Gümüşhane, Hatay, İstanbul, İzmir, Kars, Kastamonu, Kayseri, Kırşehir, Kocaeli, Malatya, Mardin, Mersin, Muğla, Muş, Osmaniye, Rize, Samsun, Sinop, Tokat, Trabzon, Tunceli (Horváth, 1901; Kiritshenko, 1924; Hoberlandt, 1955; Önder et al., 2006; Dursun & Fent, 2009; Yıldırım et al., 2011, 2013a; Matocq et al., 2014; Küçükbasmacı & Kıyak, 2015; Fent & Dursun, 2019; Zengin & Dursun, 2019; Akman & Dursun, 2021; Çerçi & Özgen, 2021; Kıyak & Baş, 2021; Yazıcı, 2022).

Genus: *Spathocera* Stein, 1860***Spathocera lobata* (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1840)**

Pseudophloeus lobatus Herrich-Schaeffer, 1840.

Material examined: Çankırı Prov.: Ilgaz, Belören, 40°52'11"N, 33°29'39"E, 1543 m, 25.VII.2013, ♀.

Previous records: Bursa, Çorum, Erzurum, Kars, Kırklareli, Konya, Van (Önder et al., 2006; Dursun, 2011b; Yıldırım et al., 2011, 2013a; Dursun & Fent, 2015; Akman & Dursun, 2021).

Genus: *Syromastus* Berthold, 1827

***Syromastus rhombeus* (Linnaeus, 1767)**

Cimex rhombeus Linnaeus, 1767; *Cimex quadratus* Fabricius, 1775; *Verlusia sinuata* Fieber, 1861; *Verlusia rhombea* var. *fusca* Vidal, 1936.

Material examined: Çankırı Prov.: Ilgaz, Belören, 40°52'11"N, 33°29'39"E, 1543 m, 25.07.2013, ♂; Çerkeş, between Yıprak-Tohumlar villages, 40°55'1"N, 32°48'34"E, 1153 m, 26.08.2013, ♀.

Previous records: Adana, Ağrı, Amasya, Ankara, Artvin, Aydın, Balıkesir, Burdur, Bursa, Çankırı, Çorum, Edirne, Elazığ, Erzurum, Gaziantep, Hatay, Isparta, İstanbul, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Kars, Kayseri, Kastamonu, Manisa, Mersin, Nevşehir, Sivas, Sinop, Tokat, Van (Horváth, 1883, 1901; Kiritshenko, 1918, 1924; Hoberlandt, 1955; Linnavuori, 1965; Tuatay et al., 1972; Kıyak et al., 2004; Önder et al., 2006; Dursun & Fent, 2009; Dursun, 2011b; Yıldırım et al., 2011, 2013a; Çerçi et al., 2018; Fent & Dursun, 2019; Zengin & Dursun, 2019; Akman & Dursun, 2021; Kıyak & Baş, 2021; Yazıcı, 2022).

Subfamily: Pseudophloeinae Stal, 1868

Tribe: Pseudophloeini Stal, 1873

Genus: *Coriomeris* Westwood, 1842

***Coriomeris denticulatus* (Scopoli, 1763)**

Cimex denticulatus Scopoli, 1763; *Cimex spinosulus* Sulzer, 1776; *Coreus pilicornis* Burmeister, 1835; *Coreus wolffi* Gorski, 1852; *Coriomeris denticulatus* var. *granulatus* Cerutti, 1937.

Material examined: Çankırı Prov.: Yapraklı, Söğütlü village, 40°40'38"N, 33°57'41"E, 1376 m, 24.VII.2013, ♀; Ilgaz, Belören, 40°52'11"N, 33°29'39"E, 1543 m, 25.VII.2013, ♀.

Previous records: Adana, Ağrı, Amasya, Ankara, Aydın, Balıkesir, Bursa, Çankırı, Çorum, Denizli, Diyarbakır, Edirne, Erzurum, Giresun, Hatay, Iğdır, Isparta, İzmir, Kars, Kayseri, Konya, Mersin, Sivas, Tokat (Kiritshenko, 1918; Linnavuori, 1965; Önder et al., 2006; Dursun & Fent, 2009; Dursun, 2011b; Fent & Japoshvili, 2012; Yıldırım et al., 2013a; Zengin & Dursun, 2019; Bolu, 2020; Akman & Dursun, 2021; Bulak & Yıldırım, 2021; Kıyak & Baş, 2021).

Family CYDNIDAE Bilberg, 1820

Subfamily: Shirinae Amyot & Serville, 1843

Tribe: Shirini Amyot & Serville, 1843

Genus: *Canthophorus* Mulsant & Rey, 1866

***Canthophorus melanopterus melanopterus* (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1835)**

Cydnus melanopterus Herrich-Schaeffer, 1835

Material examined: Çankırı prov.: Korgun, between Karatekin and Yolkaya village, 40°41'30" N, 33°29'20"E, 957 m, 22.04.2013, ♀.

Previous records: Erzurum, İstanbul, Kırklareli (Fent & Aktaç, 2009; Yazıcı et al., 2015a).

Genus: *Legnotus* Schiodte, 1848***Legnotus picipes* (Fallén, 1807)**

Cydnus picipes Fallén, 1807; *Gnathoconus costalis* Fieber, 1861; *Gnathoconus concolor* var. *cyaneonitens* Ferrari, 1874.

Material examined: Çankırı prov.: Kalecik-Çankırı provincial border D-765 Highway, 40°21'28"N, 33°31'0"E, 701 m, 21.IV.2013, ♂.

Previous records: Erzurum (Yazıcı et al., 2015a).

Genus: *Ochetostethus* Fieber, 1860***Ochetostethus opacus* (Scholtz, 1847)**

Cydnus opacus Scholtz, 1847.

Material examined: Çankırı Prov.: 2. km from Çankırı exit to Yapraklı, 40°35'57"N, 33°37'12"E, 730 m, 23.VII.2013, ♀.

Previous records: Adana, Antalya, Çorum, Edirne, Erzurum Gaziantep, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Karaman, Kayseri, Konya, Manisa, Mersin, Osmaniye, Tekirdağ (Önder et al., 2006; Fent & Aktaş, 2009; Yazıcı et al., 2015a; Yazıcı, 2022).

Genus: *Sehirus* Amyot & Serville, 1843***Sehirus dissimilis* Horváth, 1919**

Sehirus dissimilis Horváth, 1919.

Material examined: Çankırı Prov.: Korgun, Ildızım village entry, 40°42'31"N, 33°28'3"E, 1031 m, 23.04.2013, ♀.

Previous records: Ardahan, Erzurum, Kahramanmaraş (Önder et al., 2006; Yazıcı et al., 2015a).

Genus: *Tritomegas* Amyot & Serville, 1843***Tritomegas sexmaculatus* (Rambur, 1839)**

Cydnus sexmaculatus Rambur, 1839

Material examined: Çankırı Prov.: Eldivan, Eldivan entry, 40°32'25"N, 33°30'18"E, 922 m, 23.IV.2013, ♀.

Previous records: Adana, Ankara, Aradahan, Edirne, Erzurum, İstanbul, Kırklareli, Mersin, Samsun, Tekirdağ (Hoberlandt, 1955; Fent & Aktaş, 2009; Yazıcı et al., 2015a).

Family: LYGAEIDAE Schilling, 1829**Subfamily: Cyminae Boerensprung, 1860****Tribe: Cymini Boerensprung, 1860****Genus: *Cymus* Hahn, 1832*****Cymus melanocephalus* Fieber, 1861**

Cymus melanocephalus Fieber, 1861

Material examined: Çankırı Prov.: Çerkeş, Akbaş village, 40° 53' 26" N, 32° 49' 36" E, 1230 m 25.08.2013, 2 ♀♀, ♂; Şabanözü, Gümerdiğin, 40°26'40"N, 33°17'2"E, 990 m 24.04.2013, ♀.

Previous records: Adana, Ankara, Antalya, Bartın, Bayburt, Bolu, Bursa, Çanak-kale, Edirne, Erzincan, Erzurum, Gaziantep, Hatay, İstanbul, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Kastamonu, Kırşehir, Kocaeli, Konya, Mersin, Muğla, Nevşehir, Niğde, Ordu, Sinop, Sivas, Yozgat, Zonguldak, (Lodos et al., 1999; Kiyak et al., 2004; Önder et al., 2006; Yazıcı et al., 2015).

Genus: *Geocoris* Fallén, 1814***Geocoris (Piocoris) erythrocephalus* (Lepelletier & Serville, 1825)**

Salda erythrocephala Lepelletier & Serville, 1825; *Cimex grylloides* Linnaeus, 1767; *Ophthalmicus frontalis* Herrich-Schaeffer, 1837; *Salda orsiniana* A. Costa, 1839;

Geocoris erythrocephalus var. *litoreus* Horváth, 1895.

Material examined: Çankırı Prov.: Çerkeş, between Türbaşı and Dağçukurören village, 40°44'39"N, 32°50'14"E, 1271 m, 29.08.2013, 1♀.

Previous records: Adana, Afyonkarahisar, Amasya, Ankara, Antalya, Aydın, Balıkesir, Bartın, Bilecik, Bolu, Burdur, Bursa, Çanakkale, Çankırı, Çorum, Denizli, Diyarbakır, Edirne, Elazığ, Erzincan, Erzurum, Gaziantep, Gümüşhane, Hatay, Isparta, İstanbul, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Karaman, Kars, Kastamonu, Kayseri, Konya, Kütahya, Malatya, Manisa, Mardin, Mersin, Muğla, Nevşehir, Niğde, Siirt, Şanlıurfa, Tekirdağ, Trabzon, Uşak, Yozgat, Zonguldak (Hoberlandt, 1955; Çakır & Önder, 1990; Kıyak et al., 2004; Matocq et al., 2014; Yazıcı et al., 2015b; Çerçi et al., 2018; Yazıcı, 2019; Çerçi & Özgen, 2021; Yılmaz & Dursun, 2022).

Subfamily: Lygaeinae Schilling, 1829

Genus: *Lygaeus* Fabricius, 1794

Lygaeus equestris (Linnaeus, 1758)

Cimex equestris Linnaeus, 1758; *Cimex speciosus* Poda, 1761; *Cimex hyosciami* (non Linnaeus, 1758); *Cimex punctumalbum* Pollich, 1781; *Lygaeus equestris* var. *lactans* Horváth, 1899.

Material examined: Çankırı Prov.: Korgun, Yukarıçavuş village, 40°42'22"N, 33°38'59"E, 940 m, 21.IV.2013, ♀; Korgun, Akçavakıf, 40°41'40"N, 33°33'37"E, 826 m, 22.IV.2013, 2♀♀; Korgun, Yolcaya village, 40°40'41"N, 33°27'33"E, 995 m 22.IV.2013, 3♀♀, 5♂♂; Ilgaz, Yaylaören village distinction, 40°52'42"N, 33°30'31"E, 914 m, 22.IV.2013, 3♀♀, 2♂♂; Eldivan, Eldivan entrance, 40°32'25"N, 33°30'18"E, 922 m 23.IV.2013, ♀; Ilgaz, Belören, 40°52'11"N, 33°29'39"E, 1543 m, 25.VII.2013, ♂; Ilgaz, Eskikiymık village entrance, 41°0'19"N, 33°41'15"E, 1230 m, 26.VII.2013, 3♀♀, ♂; Kurşunlu, between Madenli village and Çaylıca, 40°56'23"N, 33°12'24"E, 900 m, 27.VII.2013, ♂; Atkaracalar, Höyük village, 40°48'28"N, 33°3'47"E, 1239 m, 27.VII.2013, ♂; Atkaracalar, between Budakpınarı and Yakalı villages, 40°53'26"N, 33°8'58"E, 1314 m, 25.VIII.2013, ♂; Çerkeş, Aliözü village exit (towards the highway), 40°49'40"N, 32°56'49"E, 1231 m, 26.VIII.2013, ♀; Bayramören, between piriçli and Sazak village, 40°58'20"N, 33°4'47"E, 1630 m, 27.VIII.2013, ♂; Çerkeş, between Kadılar and Dikenli plateau, 40°47'35"N, 32°44'35"E, 1449 m, 28.VIII.2013, 2♀♀, 2♂♂; Çerkeş, between Kısaç and Bozcaarmut villages, 40°41'35"N, 32°50'27"E, 1600 m, 29.VIII.2013, 2♀♀; Çerkeş, between Dere and Suluk plateau, 40°42'44"N, 32°52'56"E, 1422 m, 29.VIII.2013, ♀, ♂.

Previous records: Adana, Afyon, Amasya, Ankara, Antalya, Artvin, Aydın, Balıkesir, Bayburt, Bingöl, Çankırı, Denizli, Diyarbakır, Elazığ, Erzincan, Erzurum, Giresun, Hayat, Iğdır, Isparta, İstanbul, Kahramanmaraş, Karabük, Kars, Kastamonu, Konya, Malatya, Manisa, Mersin, Nevşehir, Osmaniye, Rize, Sivas, Trabzon, Tunceli (Horváth, 1901; Linnavuori, 1965; Kıyak et al., 2004; Fent & Japoshvili, 2012; Matocq et al., 2014; Küçükbasmacı & Kıyak, 2015; Yazıcı et al., 2015b; Çerçi et al., 2018; Bolu, 2020; Çerçi & Özgen, 2021).

Genus: *Spilostethus* Stål, 1868

Spilostethus saxatilis (Scopoli, 1763)

Cimex saxatilis Scopoli, 1763; *Cimex tessellatus* Goeze, 1778; *Lygaeus lusitanicus* Herrich-Schaeffer, 1850; *Lygaeus saxatilis* var. *montivagus* Horváth, 1899; *Spilostethus (Lygaeus) saxatilis* f. *juncta* Priesner, 1927; *Spilostethus (Lygaeus) saxatilis* f. *rupta* Priesner, 1927; *Lygaeus saxatilis* f. *montana* Tamanini, 1961; *Lygaeus saxatilis* f. *citrina* Tamanini, 1961.

Material examined: Çankırı Prov.: Ilgaz, Ilgaz exit-Gircen, 40°54'55"N,

33°37'41"E, 887 m, 22.IV.2013, ♀.

Previous records: Adana, Aksaray, Ankara, Ardahan, Balıkesir, Burdur, Diyarbakır, Elazığ, Erzincan, Erzurum, Eskişehir, Gaziantep, Kars, Kastamonu, Konya, Malatya, Mersin, Nevşehir, Sivas, Tunceli, Yozgat (Hoberlandt, 1955; Kıyak et al., 2004; Fent & Japoshvili, 2012; Matocq et al., 2014; Küçükbasmacı & Kıyak, 2015; Yazıcı et al., 2015b; Çerçi et al., 2018; Bolu, 2020; Çerçi & Özgen, 2021; Yazıcı, 2022).

Genus: *Tropidothorax* Bergroth, 1894

***Tropidothorax leucopterus* (Goeze, 1778)**

Cimex leucopterus Goeze, 1778; *Cimex familiaris* Fabricius, 1781; *Cimex stellifer* Geoffroy in Fourcroy, 1785; *Cimex raii* Turton, 1802; *Lygaeus venustus* Herrich-Schaeffer, 1835; *Lygaeus simla* Distant, 1909; *Lygaeus familiaris* var. *aurantiaca* Thierry-Mieg, 1913; *Lygaeus familiaris* var. *flavina* Thierry-Mieg, 1913; *Lygaeus leucopterus* var. *incarnatus* Seabra, 1924.

Material examined: Çankırı Prov.: Kalecik-Çankırı provincial border D-765 Highway, 40°21'28"N, 33°31'0"E, 701 m, 21.IV.2013, ♀.

Previous records: Ankara, Antalya, Artvin, Bursa, Çorum, Erzincan, Erzurum, Iğdır, Kastamonu, Konya, Manisa, Niğde, Zonguldak (Önder et al., 2006; Yazıcı et al., 2015b; Yazıcı, 2022)

Subfamily: Oxycareninae Stål, 1862

Genus: *Metopoplax* Fieber, 1860

***Metopoplax ditomoides* (A. Costa, 1847)**

Pachymerus ditomoides A. Costa, 1847

Material examined: Çankırı Prov.: Şabanözü, 3. km between Şabanözü-Eldivan road, 40°28'48"N, 33°18'37"E, 1141 m, 24.IV.2013, ♀.

Previous records: New record for Türkiye fauna.

Subfamily: Oxycareninae Stål, 1862

Tribes: Rhyparochromini Amyot & Serville, 1843

Genus: *Raglius* Stål, 1872

***Raglius alboacuminatus* (Goeze, 1778)**

Cimex alboacuminatus Goeze, 1778; *Cimex caffer* Thunberg, 1784; *Cimex apicaris* Geoffroy in Fourcroy, 1785; *Cimex cinereus* Gmelin, 1790; *Cimex bardanae* Preyssl, 1791; *Lygaeus pedestris* Panzer, 1797; *Pachymerus insignis* Boheman, 1852; *Rhyparochromus mundulus* Dohrn, 1860; *Rhyparochromus concinnulus* Walker, 1872; *Pachymerus pedestris* var. *funerea* Puton, 1878; *Pachymerus bardanae* var. *flavatus* Horváth, 1882; *Aphanus alboacuminatus* var. *bicolor* Horváth, 1911; *Rhyparochromus alboacuminatus* f. *immaculata* Michalk, 1938; *Rhyparochromus alboacuminatus* f. *nigra* Michalk, 1938; *Rhyparochromus alboacuminatus* f. *implagiata* Stichel, 1962.

Material examined: Çankırı Prov.: Çerkeş, Forest area ahead of Quail Plateau, 40°39'10"N, 32°52'4"E, 1800 m, 29.VIII.2013, ♂.

Previous records: Balıkesir, Muş (Abacıgil et al., 2010; Çerçi et al., 2018).

Genus: *Rhyparochromus* Hahn, 1826

***Rhyparochromus sanguineus* (Douglas & Scott, 1868)**

Calyptonotus sanguineus Douglas & Scott, 1868

Material examined: Çankırı Prov.: Atkaracalar, Höyük village, 40°48'28"N, 33°3'47"E, 1239 m, 27.VII.2013, ♂.

Previous records: Bingöl, Diyarbakır, Erzincan, Erzurum, Mardin, Tunceli (Matocq et al., 2014; Yazıcı et al., 2015b; Çerçi et al., 2018).

***Rhyparochromus vulgaris* (Schilling, 1829)**

Pachymerus vulgaris Schilling, 1829; *Lygaeus pini* (non Linnaeus, 1758): Wolff, 1801; *Aphanus vulgaris* var. *homoeopus* Horváth, 1899

Material examined: Çankırı Prov.: Çerkeş, Kuzuören village, 40°53'35"N, 32°52'32"E, 1304 m, 25.VIII.2013, ♂; Çerkeş, between Yakuplar and Örenköy, 40°44'44"N, 32°52'25"E, 1301 m, 29.VIII.2013, ♀.

Previous records: Adana, Ankara, Aydın, Balıkesir, Bursa, Çanakkale, Edirne, Erzincan, Erzurum, Hatay, İzmir, Kütahya, Manisa, Mersin, Muğla, Tunceli, Uşak (Önder et al., 2006; Fent & Japoshvili, 2012; Yazıcı et al., 2015b).

Genus: *Xanthochilus* Stål, 1872

***Xanthochilus minusculus* (Reuter, 1885)**

Pachymerus (Xanthochilus) minusculus Reuter, 1885; *Pachymerus (Xanthochilus) reuteri* Horváth, 1885.

Material examined: Çankırı Prov.: Çerkeş, between Kadılar – Dikenli Plateau, 40°47'35"N, 32°44'35"E, 1449 m, 28.VIII.2013, ♀.

Previous records: Elazığ, Siirt (Matocq et al., 2014; Bolu, 2020; Çerçi & Özgen, 2021).

Family NABIDAE Costa, 1853

Subfamily: Prostematinae Reuter, 1890

Tribe: Prostematini Reuter, 1890

Genus: *Prostemma* Laporte, 1832

Subgenus: *Prostemma* Laporte, 1832

***Prostemma (Prostemma) guttula guttula* (Fabricius, 1787)**

Reduvius guttula Fabricius, 1787; *Cimex staphylinus* Gmelin, 1790; *Prostemma brachelytrum* Dufour, 1834; *Prostemma fuscipenne* Mulsant & Rey, 1873.

Material examined: Çankırı Prov.: Çerkeş, Kuzuören village, 40°53'35"N, 32°52'32"E, 1304 m, 25.VIII.2013, ♀.

Previous records: Thrace region (Fent & Japoshvili, 2012).

Subfamily: Nabinae A. Costa, 1853

Tribe: Nabini A. Costa, 1853

Genus: *Nabis* Latreille, 1802

Subgenus: *Nabis* Latreille, 1802

***Nabis (Nabis) pseudoferus pseudoferus* Remane, 1949**

Nabis pseudoferus Remane, 1949; *Nabis pseudoferus* f. *maculatus* Remane, 1949.

Material examined: Çankırı Prov.: Eldivan, Maruf village, 40°38'26"N, 33°25'59"E, 1196 m, 23.IV.2013, ♀; Eldivan, Eldivan entry, 40°32'25"N, 33°30'18"E, 922 m, 23.IV.2013, 2 ♀♀, 2 ♂♂; Çankırı, Orta, Yaylakent Town distinction, 40°36'28"N, 33°7'17"E, 1257 m, 24.IV.2013, ♂; Şabanözü, Gümerdiğin, 40°26'40"N, 33°17'2"E, 990 m, 24.IV.2013, ♀; Çankırı, Merkez, Hasakça village distinction, 40°39'59"N, 33°44'28"E, 863 m, 24.VII.2013, ♂; Ilgaz, Yuvasaray village entry, 40°52'26"N, 33°44'36"E, 902 m 25.VII.2013, 2 ♀♀, 4 ♂♂; Ilgaz, Yuvasaray village exit 4. km from Yukarioz, 40°52'8"N, 33°46'27"E, 1101 m, 25.VII.2013, 2 ♀♀; Çerkeş, Yoncalı village return, 40°42'13"N, 32°46'26"E, 1314 m 27.VII.2013, ♂; Çerkeş, Forest area beyond Yeşilören village, 40°47'32"N, 32°35'12"E, 1597 m, 28.VIII.2013, ♀; Çerkeş, Dağçukurören village, 40°44'32"N, 32°50'17"E, 1271 m, 29.08.2013, 2 ♂♂; Çerkeş,

between Yakuplar- Örenköy, 40°44'44"N, 32°52'25"E, 1301 m 29.VIII.2013, ♀.

Previous records: Adana, Adıyaman, Amasya, Ankara, Artvin, Bartın, Bayburt, Edirne, Erzincan, Erzurum, Giresun, Gümüşhane, Iğdır, Kars, Kastamonu, Sivas, Tokat, Trabzon (Hoberlandt, 1955; Tuatay et al., 1972; Önder et al., 2006; Dursun, 2011a; Yıldırım et al., 2013b; Küçükbasmacı & Kiyak, 2015; Yazıcı, 2022).

***Nabis (Nabis) rugosus* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Cimex rugosus Linnaeus, 1758; *Cimex conicus* Goeze, 1778; *Nabis fuminervis* Dahlbom, 1851; *Nabis rugosus* var. *nervosus* Rey, 1893; *Reduviolus rugosus* var. *pallidorsum* Reuter, 1908.

Material examined: Çankırı Prov.: Ilgaz, Ilgaz exit-Gircen, 40°54'55"N, 33°37'41"E, 887 m, 22.IV.2013, ♀; Orta, Return to Yaylakent town, 40°36'28"N, 33°7'17"E, 1257 m 24.IV.2013, ♂.

Previous records: Ardahan, Artvin, Aydın, Bolu, Burdur, Çankırı, Çorum, Edirne, Elazığ, Giresun, Gümüşhane, İzmir, Kars, Kocaeli, Samsun, Tokat, Zonguldak (Kiritshenko, 1918; Önder et al., 2006; Dursun, 2011a).

Family PLATASPIDAE Dallas, 1851

Subfamily: Coptosomatinae Kirkaldy, 1909

Genus: *Coptosoma* Laporte, 1833

***Coptosoma scutellatum* (Geoffroy, 1785)**

Cimex scutellatus Geoffroy in Fourcroy, 1785; *Cimex scarabaeoides* (non Linnaeus, 1758): Sulzer, 1761; *Cimex globus* Fabricius, 1794; *Coptosoma dilatata* Motschulsky, 1860; *Coptosoma anatolica* Horváth, 1883; *Coptosoma scutellatum* f. *violacea* Davidová-Vilimová & Štys, 1980.

Material examined: Çankırı Prov.: Kızılırmak, between Yukarıalagöz and Alaca Village, 40°22'28"N, 33°54'54"E, 619 m, 25.IV.2014, ♀.

Previous records: Ankara, Bayburt, Çanakkale, Edirne, Erzincan, Erzurum, İstanbul, Kahramanmaraş, Kırklareli, Nevşehir, Tekirdağ (Horváth, 1901; Hoberlandt, 1955; Kiyak et al., 2004; Fent & Aktaç, 2009; Yıldırım et al., 2014b).

Family: PYRRHOCORIDAE Fieber, 1860

Genus: *Pyrrhocoris* Fallén, 1814

***Pyrrhocoris apterus* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Cimex apterus Linnaeus, 1758; *Cimex gregarius* Goeze, 1778; *Pyrrhocoris calmariensis* Fallén, 1829; *Pyrrhocoris sordidus* Jakovlev, 1880; *Pyrrhocoris apterus* var. *membranacea* Westhoff, 1884; *Pyrrhocoris apterus* var. *pennata* Westhoff, 1884; *Pyrrhocoris apterus* var. *carbonarius* Horváth, 1895; *Pyrrhocoris apterus* f. *cor* Schulze, 1917; *Pyrrhocoris apterus* f. *crassipuncta* Schulze, 1917; *Pyrrhocoris apterus* f. *strigata* Schulze, 1917; *Pyrrhocoris apterus* f. *radiata* Schulze, 1917; *Pyrrhocoris apterus* var. *hilaris* Horváth, 1917; *Pyrrhocoris apterus* var. *lagenifer* Horváth, 1917; *Pyrrhocoris apterus* f. *citrina* Schumacher, 1918; *Pyrrhocoris apterus* f. *inaequalis* Stichel, 1925; *Pyrrhocoris apterus* f. *punctella* Stichel, 1925; *Pyrrhocoris apterus* f. *trifida* Stichel, 1925; *Pyrrhocoris apterus* f. *sexpunctata* Priesner, 1927; *Pyrrhocoris apterus* f. *gigas* Kormilev, 1939; *Pyrrhocoris apterus* f. *ochracea* Wagner, 1948; *Pyrrhocoris apterus* f. *vacata* Stichel, 1959; *Pyrrhocoris pseudoapterus* Ahmad & Perveen, 1986.

Material examined: Çankırı Prov.: Kalecik-Çankırı provincial border D-765 Highway, 40°21'28"N, 33°31'0"E, 701 m, 21.IV.2013, 2 ♀♀; Eldivan, Eldivan entry, 40°32'25"N, 33°30'18"E, 922 m, 23.IV.2013, ♀; 2 km from Çankırı exit to Yapraklı, 40°35'57"N, 33°37'12"E, 730 m, 23.VII.2013, ♂.

Previous records: Adana, Adıyaman, Ağrı, Ankara, Antalya, Ardahan, Artvin, Aydın, Bayburt, Bilecik, Burdur, Bursa, Çanakkale, Çankırı, Çorum, Denizli, Edirne, Elazığ, Erzincan, Erzurum, Eskişehir, Giresun, Hatay, Iğdır, Isparta, İstanbul, Kahramanmaraş, Karaman, Kars, Kastamonu, Kayseri, Konya, Malatya, Mardin, Mersin, Muğla, Nevşehir, Niğde, Sakarya, Siirt, Sivas, Şanlıurfa, Tokat, Trabzon (Horváth, 1901; Hoberlandt, 1955; Kıyak et al., 2004; Önder et al., 2006; Matocq et al., 2014; Küçükbasmacı & Kıyak, 2015; Yıldırım et al., 2015b; Bolu, 2020; Yazıcı, 2022).

***Pyrrhocoris marginatus* (Kolenati, 1845)**

Platygaster marginatus Kolenati, 1845

Material examined: **Çankırı Prov.:** Çerkeş, On the road between Kadiözü and Ali-özü villages, 40°49'26"N, 32°57'49"E, 1257 m, 26.VIII.2013, ♀.

Previous records: Ankara, Erzurum, Hatay, Kahramanmaraş, Kayseri (Önder et al., 2006; Yazıcı et al., 2015b).

Family REDUVIDAE Latreille, 1807

Subfamily: Harpactorinae Amyot & Serville, 1843

Tribe: Harpactorini Amyot & Serville, 1843

Genus: *Rhynocoris* Hahn, 1853

Subgenus: *Rhynocoris* Hahn, 1853

***Rhynocoris punctiventris* (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1846)**

Harpactor punctiventris Herrich-Schaeffer, 1846; *Harpactor variegatus* Fieber, 1861; *Rhynocoris punctiventris* f. *uniannulata* Stichel in Dispons & Stichel, 1959; *Rhynocoris punctiventris* var. *dimidiatus* Dispons, 1964.

Material examined: **Çankırı Prov.:** 2 km from Çankırı exit to Yapraklı, 40°35'57"N, 33°37'12"E, 730 m, 23.VII.2013, ♀.

Previous records: Adana, Adıyaman, Antalya, Ardahan, Artvin, Aydın, Balıkesir, Bayburt, Bingöl, Çankırı, Diyarbakır, Elazığ, Erzincan, Erzurum, Hatay, Iğdır, İstanbul, İzmir, Kars, Kastamonu, Konya, Malatya, Manisa, Mersin, Muğla, Nevşehir, Niğde, Osmaniye, Rize, Şanlıurfa, Tunceli (Linnavuori, 1965; Kıyak et al., 2004; Yıldırım et al., 2010, 2013b; Matocq et al., 2014; Küçükbasmacı & Kıyak, 2015; Çerçi et al., 2018; Bolu, 2020).

Genus: *Sphedanolestes*, Stål, 1867

Subgenus: *Sphedanolestes* Stål, 1867

***Sphedanolestes (Sphedanolestes) pulchellus* (Klug, 1830)**

Reduvius pulchellus Klug, 1830; *Harpactor hedenborgi* Stål, 1855; *Sphedanolestes dorchymonti* Dispons, 1968.

Material examined: **Çankırı Prov.:** Ilgaz, Yuvasaray village exit 4. km from Yukarıoz, 40°52'8"N, 33°46'27"E, 1101 m, 25.VII.2013, ♀.

Previous records: Adana, Ankara, Bursa, Çankırı, Diyarbakır, Hatay, İstanbul, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Kocaeli, Nevşehir (Linnavuori, 1965; Kıyak et al., 2004; Önder et al., 2006; Matocq et al., 2014; Küçükbasmacı & Kıyak, 2015).

Family RHOPALIDAE Amyot & Serville, 1843

Subfamily: Rhopalinae Amyot & Serville, 1843

Tribe: Rhopolini Amyot & Serville, 1843

Genus: *Corizus* Fallén, 1814

***Corizus hyoscyami hyoscyami* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Cimex hyoscyami Linnaeus, 1758; *Therapha hyosciami* var. *flavicans* Puton, 1881;

Therapha hyosciami var. *usticensis* Riggio, 1885; *Therapha [hyoscyami]* var. *flavescens* Rey, 1888; *Consius collinus* Distant, 1909; *Corizus monticola* Horváth, 1917; *Therapha atropyga* Blöte, 1934.

Material examined: Çankırı Prov.: Korgun, Yukarıçavuş village 40°42'22"N, 33°38'59"E, 940 m, 21.IV.2013, ♂; Korgun, Akçavakıf, 40°41'40"N, 33°33'37"E, 826 m, 22.IV.2013, ♂; Ilgaz, Yaylaören village distinction, 40°52'42"N, 33°30'31"E, 914 m, 22.IV.2013, 2 ♂♂; Ilgaz, Kayı village exit, 40°53'44"N, 33°28'33"E, 1182 m, 22.IV.2013, ♂; Şabanözü, 3. km between Şabanözü-Eldivan road, 40°28'48"N, 33°18'37"E, 1141 m, 24.IV.2013, ♂; Yapraklı, Söğütlü village, 40°40'38"N, 33°57'41"E, 1376 m, 24.VII.2013, ♀; Ilgaz, Alpagut village exit, 40°55'06"N, 33°32'27"E, 1170 m, 26.VII.2013, ♀; Bayramören, Karakışla village on the road, 40°57'01"N, 33°09'27"E, 916 m, 27.VII.2013, ♀; Atkaracalar, Höyük village, 40°48'28"N, 33°3'47"E, 1239 m, 27.VII.2013, ♀, ♂; Atkaracalar, between Budakpınarı-Yakalı village, 40°53'26"N, 33°8'58"E, 1314 m, 25.VIII.2013, ♀; Çerkeş, between Çerkeş, Cedime, Çalcıören, Coroğlu villages turnout and Kabak village, 40°53'19"N, 32°54'47"E, 1557 m, 27.VIII.2013, ♀; Çerkeş, between Kısaç and Bozcaarmut villages, 40°41'35"N, 32°50'27"E, 1600 m, 29.VIII.2013, ♀; Çerkeş, between Bildircin and Bozcaarmut villages, 40°39'11"N, 32°51'59"E, 1804 m, 29.08.2013, ♂.

Previous records: Adapazarı, Amasya, Antalya, Ardahan, Artvin, Aydın, Balıkesir, Bayburt, Burdur, Çankırı, Çorum, Diyarbakır, Elazığ, Erzincan, Erzurum, Gaziantep, Giresun, Gümüşhane, Hayat, Iğdır, İstanbul, Kars, Kastamonu, Konya, Mardin, Mersin, Muş, Niğde, Sivas, Trabzon, Tokat, Tunceli (Dursun, 2009; Yıldırım et al., 2011, 2013a; Matocq et al., 2014; Küçükbasmacı & Kıyak, 2015; Çerçi et al., 2018; Zengin & Dursun, 2019; Akman & Dursun, 2021; Çerçi & Özgen, 2021).

Genus: *Liorhyssus* Stål, 1870

Liorhyssus hyalinus (Fabricius, 1794)

Lygaeus hyalinus Fabricius, 1794; *Corizus gracilis* Herrich-Schaeffer, 1835; *Corizus capensis* Germar, 1838; *Corizus truncatus* Rambur, 1839; *Corizus rubescens* Kolenati, 1845; *Merocoris maculiventris* Spinola, 1852; *Merocoris microtomus* Spinola, 1852; *Rhopalus ruber* Dallas, 1852; *Rhopalus bengalensis* Dallas, 1852; *Corizus sanguineus* A. Costa, 1853; *Corizus dilatipennis* Signoret, 1859; *Corizus variegatus* Signoret, 1859; *Corizus quadrilineatus* Signoret, 1859; *Corizus siculus* Signoret, 1859; *Corizus lugens* Signoret, 1859; *Rhopalus lugens* Stål, 1860; *Rhopalus victoris* Mulsant & Rey, 1870; *Corizus marginatus* Jakovlev, 1871; *Corizus hyalinus* var. *nigrinus* Puton, 1881; *Corizus hyalinus* var. *spathula* Rey, 1887; *Liorhyssus hyalinus* var. *rubricatus* Reuter, 1900; *Liorhyssus natalensis* var. *corallinus* Horváth, 1911; *Corizus scotti* Distant, 1913; *Corizus imperialis* Distant, 1918; *Corizus pronotalis* Distant, 1918; *Liorhyssus hyalinus* var. *pallidus* Mancini, 1935.

Material examined: Çankırı Prov.: Bayramören, Karakışla village on the road, 40°57'01"N, 33°09'27"E, 916 m, 27.VII.2013, ♀; Çerkeş, between Yıprak-Seedlar villages, 40°55'1"N, 32°48'34"E, 1153 m, 26.VIII.2013, ♂; Bayramören, between Pirinçli and Sazak villages, 40°58'20"N, 33°4'47"E, 1630 m, 27.VIII.2013, ♂; Çerkeş, Yeşilören village 40°47'32"N, 32°35'12"E, 1597 m, 28.VIII.2013, ♀; Çerkeş, between Dere and Suluk plateau, 40°42'44"N, 32°52'56"E, 1422 m, 29.VIII.2013, ♂.

Previous records: Adana, Adıyaman, Amasya, Ankara, Antalya, Artvin, Batman, Bursa, Çankırı, Çorum, Denizli, Diyarbakır, Elazığ, Erzincan, Erzurum, Gaziantep, Giresun, Hatay, Iğdır, Isparta, İstanbul, İzmir, Kars, Kastamonu, Konya, Mardin, Nevşehir, Ordu, Samsun, Siirt, Sivas, Şanlıurfa Tokat, Tunceli (Linnavuori, 1965; Kıyak et al., 2004; Dursun, 2009; Yıldırım et al., 2011, 2013a; Matocq et al., 2014; Küçükbasmacı & Kıyak, 2015; Çerçi et al., 2018; Zengin & Dursun, 2019; Bolu, 2020; Akman & Dursun, 2021; Bulak & Yıldırım, 2021; Çerçi & Özgen, 2021).

Genus: *Maccevethus* Dallas, 1852***Maccevethus corsicus corsicus* Signoret, 1862**

Maccevethus corsicus Signoret, 1862; *Maccevethus lutheri* Wagner, 1953.

Material examined: Çankırı Prov.: Eldivan, Eldivan entrance, 40°32'25"N, 33°30'18"E, 922 m, 23.IV.2013, ♀.

Previous records: Amasya, Çanakkale, Çorum, Erzurum, Giresun, Sivas, Tokat (Dursun, 2009; Yıldırım et al., 2013a; Zengin & Dursun, 2019; Akman & Dursun, 2021).

Tribe: Chorosomatini Fieber, 1860**Genus: *Myrmus* Hahn, 1832*****Myrmus miriformis miriformis* (Fallén, 1807)**

Coreus miriformis Fallén, 1807; *Lygaeus micropterus* Burrell, 1807; *Myrmus miriformis* (var.) *sublinearis* Rey, 1887; *Myrmus formosus* Jakovlev, 1904; *Myrmus parallelus* Jakovlev, 1905; *Myrmus miriformis f. gynaecoides* Priesner, 1926.

Material examined: Çankırı Prov.: Korgun, between Karatekin and Yolcaya village, 40°41'30"N, 33°29'20"E, 957 m, 22.IV.2013, ♂.

Previous records: Ağrı, Kastamonu (Önder et al., 2006; Dursun & Fent, 2015).

Genus: *Rhopalus* Schilling, 1827**Subgenus: *Aeschynteles* stål, 1872*****Rhopalus (Aeschyntelus) maculatus* (Fieber, 1837)**

Corizus maculatus Fieber, 1837; *Coreus crassicornis* Latreille, 1804; *Coreus clavicornis* Boitard, 1828; *Corizus maculatus* Herrich-Schaeffer, 1840; *Rhopalus chinensis* Dallas, 1852; *Corizus ledi* Boheman, 1852; *Corizus meridionalis* Jakovlev, 1869; *Rhopalus maculatus decolor* Wagner, 1962.

Material examined: Çankırı Prov.: Ilgaz, Aşağı bozan entry, 40°54'34"N, 33°36'16"E, 867 m, 26.VII.2013, ♀; Ilgaz, Eskikıymık village entry, 41°0'19"N, 33°41'15"E, 1230 m, 26.VII.2013, ♂; Bayramören, Karakışla village on the road, 40°57'01"N, 33°09'27"E, 916 m, 27.VII.2013, ♀, 2 ♂♂; Çerkeş, Kuzuören village, 40°53'35"N, 32°52'32"E, 1304 m, 25.VIII.2013, 3 ♀♀, 3 ♂♂.

Previous records: Adana, Adıyaman, Artvin, Bursa, Diyarbakır, Elazığ, Erzincan, Erzurum, Gaziantep, Gümüşhane, İstanbul, Kastamonu, Siirt, Sivas, Tokat (Önder et al., 2006; Dursun, 2009; Yıldırım et al., 2011, 2013a; Matocq et al., 2014; Küçükbasmacı & Kıyak, 2015; Çerçi et al., 2018; Bolu, 2020).

Subgenus: *Rhopalus* Schilling, 1827***Rhopalus (Rhopalus) parumpunctatus* Schilling, 1829**

Rhopalus parumpunctatus Schilling, 1829; *Corizus pratensis* Fallén, 1829; *Corizus parumpunctatus* var. *subspeciosa* Schumacher, 1914; *Corizus parumpunctatus f. extrema* Priesner, 1926; *Rhopalus parumpunctatus f. singeri* Wagner, 1939.

Material examined: Çankırı Prov.: Yapraklı, Söğütlü village, 40°40'38"N, 33°57'41"E, 1376 m, 24.VII.2013, ♂; Ilgaz, Yuvasaray village entry, 40°52'26"N, 33°44'36"E, 902 m, 25.VII.2013, ♂; Çankırı, Atkaracalar, Höyük village, 40°48'28"N, 33°3'47"E, 1239 m, 27.VII.2013, ♀, ♂; Çerkeş, Kuzuören village, 40°53'35"N, 32°52'32"E, 1304 m, 25.VIII.2013, ♂; Çerkeş, Forest area ahead of Bildircin Plateau, 40°39'10"N, 32°52'4"E, 1800 m., 29.VIII.2013, ♀, ♂; Çerkeş, between the Dere and Suluk plateaus, 40°42'44"N, 32°52'56"E, 1422 m, 29.VIII.2013, ♀, 2 ♂♂.

Previous records: Adana, Adıyaman, Amasya, Balıkesir, Batman, Çankırı, Çorum, Diyarbakır, Elazığ, Erzurum, Gaziantep, Giresun, Kastamonu, Kayseri, Mardin, Nevşehir, Siirt, Sivas, Şanlıurfa, Tokat (Linnavuori, 1965; Lodos et al., 1984; Kıyak et al., 2004; Dursun, 2009; Fent & Japoshvili, 2012; Yıldırım et al., 2013a; Matocq et al., 2014; Küçükbasmacı & Kıyak, 2015; Çerçi et al., 2018; Zengin & Dursun,

2019; Bolu, 2020; Akman & Dursun, 2021; Çerçi & Özgen, 2021; Kıyak & Baş, 2021).

***Rhopalus (Rhopalus) rufus* Schilling, 1829**

Rhopalus rufus Schilling, 1829.

Material examined: Çankırı Prov.: Ilgaz, Belören, 40°52'11"N, 33°29'39"E, 1543 m, 25.VII.2013, ♀.

Previous records: Adana, Antalya, Çanakkale, Erzurum, Hatay, İstanbul, Kastamonu, Konya, Nevşehir (Kıyak et al., 2004; Önder et al., 2006; Yıldırım et al., 2011; Küçükbasmacı & Kıyak, 2015;).

***Rhopalus (Rhopalus) subrufus* (Gmelin, 1790)**

Cimex subrufus Gmelin, 1790; *Cimex glutinosae* Schrank, 1785; *Lygaeus capitatus* Fabricius, 1794; *Lygaeus magnicornis* Fabricius, 1794; *Rhopalus mavromaustakisi* Wagner, 1967.

Material examined: Çankırı Prov.: Ilgaz, Yuvasaray village exit 4. km from Yukarioz, 40° 52'8"N, 33°46'27"E, 1101 m, 25.VII.2013, ♀; Çerkeş, between the villages of Kısaç and Bozcaarmut, 40°41'35"N, 32°50'27"E, 1600 m, 29.VIII.2013, ♂.

Previous records: Artvin, Çorum, Elazığ, Erzincan, Erzurum, Hatay, İstanbul, Kayseri, Mardin, Sivas, Tokat (Linnavuori, 1965; Dursun, 2009; Yıldırım et al., 2011, 2013a; Matocq et al., 2014; Akman & Dursun, 2021; Kıyak & Baş, 2021).

Genus: *Stictopleurus* stål, 1872

***Stictopleurus abutilon* (Rossi, 1790)**

Cimex abutilon Rossi, 1790; *Corizus substriatus* Burmeister, 1835; *Rhopalus abutilon* var. *flavescens* Fieber, 1861; *Rhopalus (Rhopalus) signoreti* Mulsant & Rey, 1870.

Material examined: Çankırı Prov.: Ilgaz, Ilgaz exit-Gircen, 40°54'55"N, 33°37'41"E, 887 m, 22.IV.2013, ♀; Ilgaz, Yaylaören village distinction, 40°52'42"N, 33°30'31"E, 914 m, 22.IV.2013, ♀; Eldivan, Eldivan entry, 40°32'25"N, 33°30'18"E, 922 m, 23.IV.2013, ♂; Ilgaz, Eskikiymık village entry, 41°0'19"N, 33°41'15"E, 1230 m, 26.VII.2013, ♂; Atkaracalar, between Budakpınarı village- Yakalı village, 40°53'26"N, 33°8'58"E, 1314 m, 25.VIII.2013, ♀, ♂.

Previous records: Amasya, Çorum, Diyarbakır, Elazığ, Erzincan, Erzurum, Hatay, Iğdır, Mardin, Tokat (Linnavuori, 1965; Dursun, 2009; Yıldırım et al., 2013a; Matocq et al., 2014; Çerçi et al., 2018; Zengin & Dursun, 2019; Bolu 2020; Akman & Dursun, 2021; Bulak & Yıldırım, 2021).

***Stictopleurus crassicornis* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Cimex crassicornis Linnaeus, 1758; *Cimex alatus* O.F. Müller, 1776; *Coreus cellulatus* Brullé, 1832; *Rhopalus crassicornis* var. *griseus* Fieber, 1861; *Rhopalus crassicornis* var. *maculatus* Fieber, 1861; *Corizus crassicornis* var. *pictus* Horváth, 1878; *Corizus abutilon* var. *umbrinus* Rey, 1887; *Corizus crassicornis* var. *anticus* Rey, 1888; *Corizus crassicornis* var. *maculicollis* Rey, 1888; *Stictopleurus mixtus* Ribaut, 1921; *Stictopleurus crassicornis* f. *immaculata* Tamanini, 1951; *Stictopleurus crassicornis* f. *virgata* Stichel, 1960.

Material examined: Çankırı Prov.: Between Çerkeş, Cedime, Çalcıören, Coroğlu villages turnout and Kabak village, 40°53'19"N, 32°54'47"E, 1557 m, 27.VIII.2013, ♀.

Previous records: Ankara, Bursa, Çankırı, Diyarbakır, Gümüşhane, Kars, Kastamonu, Kayseri, Konya, Tokat (Lodos et al., 1984; Önder et al., 2006; Dursun, 2009; Küçükbasmacı & Kıyak, 2015; Bolu, 2020).

***Stictopleurus punctatonervosus* (Goeze, 1778)**

Cimex punctatonervosus Goeze, 1778; *Cimex sabulosus* Geoffroy in Fourcroy, 1785; *Cimex subfuscus* Gmelin, 1790; *Stictopleurus viridescens* Lindberg, 1934; *Stictopleurus*

punctatonervosus f. *virescens* Tamanini, 1951; *Stictopleurus lauterbachii* Rieger, 1971.

Material examined: Çankırı Prov.: Kalecik-Çankırı provincial border D-765 Highway, 40°21'28"N, 33°31'0"E, 701 m, 21.IV.2013, ♀; Eldivan, Eldivan entry, 40°32'25"N, 33°30'18"E, 922 m, 23.IV.2013, ♀; Çerkeş, Dağçukurören village, 40°44'32"N, 32°50'17"E, 1271 m, 29.VIII.2013, ♀; Çerkeş, between Yakuplar and Örenköy, 40°44'44"N, 32°52'25"E, 1301 m, 29.VIII.2013, ♂; Merkez, Aşağıçavuş village, 40°41'39,7"N, 33°38'01,7"E, 880 m, 15.VII.2014, ♂.

Previous records: Antalya, Ardahan, Artvin, Aydın, Bayburt, Elazığ, Erzincan, Erzurum, Gaziantep, Giresun, Gümüşhane, Iğdır, İstanbul, İzmir, Kars, Kocaeli, Manisa, Ordu, Samsun, Sivas, Tekirdağ, Tokat, Tunceli, Yozgat (Önder et al., 2006; Dursun, 2009; Yıldırım et al., 2011, 2013a).

Family: SCUTELLERIDAE Leach, 1815

Subfamily: Eurygastrinae Amyot & Serville, 1843

Tribe: Eurygastrini Amyot & Serville, 1843

Genus: Eurygaster Laporte, 1833

***Eurygaster austriaca* (Schrank, 1776)**

Cimex austriacus Schrank, 1776; *Cimex frischii* Goeze, 1778; *Cimex schrankii* Goeze, 1778; *Cimex fuscocucullatus* Goeze, 1778; *Cimex nigrocucullatus* Goeze, 1778; *Cimex aethiops* Goeze, 1778; *Cimex truncatus* Goeze, 1778; *Cimex secalinus* Geoffroy in Fourcroy, 1785; *Cimex cappatus* Geoffroy in Fourcroy, 1785; *Cimex fuscus* Gmelin, 1790; *Cimex cucullatus* Gmelin, 1790; *Cimex carinatus* Cyrillus, 1791; *Tetyra nigra* Fabricius, 1803; *Eurygaster hottentotus* var. *communis* Fieber, 1861; *Eurygaster hottentotus* var. *lineata* Fieber, 1861; *Eurygaster hottentotus* var. *nigricans* Fieber, 1861; *Eurygaster hottentotus* var. *signata* Fieber, 1861; *Eurygaster ligneus* Vollenhoven, 1863; *Eurygaster hottentota* var. *picta* Antessanty, 1891; *Eurygaster nigrocucullata* var. *eurhemia* Kirkaldy, 1909; *Eurygaster nigrocucullata* var. *fuscescens* Kirkaldy, 1909; *Eurygaster nigrocucullatus* ab. *rufa* Péneau, 1911; *Eurygaster nigrocucullatus* var. *vittata* Péneau, 1911; *Eurygaster austriaca seabrai* CH, 1938; *Eurygaster austriacus* f. *marginata* Kupka, 1944; *Eurygaster austriaca* var. *calligera* Wagner, 1951; *Eurygaster austriaca* var. *extensa* Wagner, 1951; *Eurygaster austriaca* var. *ornata* Wagner, 1951; *Eurygaster austriaca* var. *purpurascens* Wagner, 1951v; *Eurygaster austriaca* ab. *ochroleuca* Halászfy, 1959; *Eurygaster austriaca austriaca* f. *simulata* Stichel, 1960; *Eurygaster austriacus* var. *seminigra* Lodos, 1960; *Eurygaster austriaca seabrai* f. *rubra* Fuente, 1974; *Eurygaster austriaca seabrai* f. *pseudomarginata* Fuente, 1974.

Material examined: Çankırı Prov.: Korgun, Yolcaya village, 40°40'41"N, 33°27'33"E, 995 m, 22.IV.2013, ♀.

Previous records: Adana, Adıyaman, Ankara, Antalya, Balıkesir, Bilecik, Çanak-kale, Çankırı, Edirne, Erzincan, Erzurum, Eskişehir, Iğdır, Isparta, İstanbul, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Karabük, Karaman, Kastamonu, Kırıkkale, Kırklareli, Konya, Mersin, Muş, Tekirdağ, Trabzon, Tunceli (Önder et al., 2006; Fent & Aktaş, 2009; Fent & Japoshvili, 2012; Yıldırım et al., 2014a; Küçükbasmacı & Kıyak, 2015).

***Eurygaster dilaticollis* Dohrn, 1860**

Eurygaster dilaticollis Dohrn, 1860; *Eurygaster brevicollis* Fieber, 1861; *Eurygaster schreiberi* Montandon, 1885; *Eurygaster schreiberi* var. *flavescens* Horváth, 1911; *Eurygaster maura* f. *improvisa* Wagner, 1940; *Eurygaster schreiberi* var. *bimaculata* Wagner, 1951; *Eurygaster schreiberi* var. *discreta* Wagner, 1951; *Eurygaster schreiberi* var. *marginella* Wagner, 1951; *Eurygaster schreiberi* var. *nigrofusca* Wagner, 1951; *Eurygaster schreiberi* var. *rufobrunnea* Wagner, 1951; *Eurygaster schreiberi* var. *saulii* Wagner, 1951; *Eurygaster dilaticollis* var. *decorata* Wagner, 1951; *Eurygaster*

dilaticollis var. *expansa* Wagner, 1951; *Eurygaster dilaticollis* var. *straminea* Wagner, 1951; *Eurygaster dilaticollis* ab. *umbrina* Halászfy, 1959; *Eurygaster schreiberi* ab. *erubescens* Halászfy, 1959.

Material examined: Çankırı Prov.: Bayramören, Sazak- Karaoluk villages junction, 40°57'54"N, 33°4'1"E, 1578 m, 27.VIII.2013, ♂.

Previous records: Ağrı, Ankara, Ardahan, Artvin, Balıkesir, Erzincan, Erzurum, Kars, Konya (Kiritshenko 1918; Önder et al., 2006; Fent & Japoshvili, 2012; Yıldırım et al., 2014a).

***Eurygaster maura* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Cimex maurus Linnaeus, 1758; *Cimex cinereus* Goeze, 1778; *Tetyra picta* Fabricius, 1803; *Eurygaster maura* var. *communis* Fieber, 1861; *Eurygaster minor* Montandon, 1885; *Eurygaster maura* f. *meridionalis* Péneau, 1911; *Eurygaster maura* ab. *rufopicta* Péneau, 1911; *Eurygaster maurus* f. *personatus* Stichel, 1924; *Eurygaster meridionalis* var. *nigricans* Mancini, 1931; *Eurygaster meridionalis* var. *maculata* Mancini, 1931; *Eurygaster maurus* f. *aequalis* Wagner, 1938; *Eurygaster maurus* f. *granulosus* Wagner, 1938; *Eurygaster maurus* f. *pallidus* Wagner, 1938; *Eurygaster maurus* var. *rutilus* Wagner, 1938; *Eurygaster maura* var. *punctata* Wagner, 1951; *Eurygaster maura* ab. *pallens* Halászfy, 1959; *Eurygaster maura* ab. *melanaria* Halászfy, 1959; *Eurygaster maura* ab. *rubida* Halászfy, 1959; *Eurygaster maura* ab. *umbrosa* Halászfy, 1959; *Eurygaster maura* f. *subnigra* Stichel, 1960.

Material examined: Çankırı Prov.: Şabanözü, 3. km between Şabanözü-Eldivan road, 40°28'48"N, 33°18'37"E, 1141 m, 24.IV.2013, ♂; Atkaracalar, Höyük village, 40°48'28"N, 33°3'47"E, 1239 m, 27.VII.2013, ♀.

Previous records: Adana, Adıyaman, Aksaray, Ankara, Antalya, Ardahan, Artvin, Balıkesir, Bayburt, Bilecik, Çanakkale, Çankırı, Denizli, Edirne, Elazığ, Erzincan, Erzurum, Iğdır, Isparta, İstanbul, Karaman, Kars, Kastamonu, Kayseri, Kırıkkale, Kırklareli, Kırşehir, Konya, Malatya, Nevşehir, Tekirdağ (Kiyak et al., 2004; Fent & Aktaş 2009; Fent & Japoshvili, 2012; Matocq et al., 2014; Yıldırım et al., 2014a; Küçükbasmacı & Kiyak, 2015).

***Eurygaster testudinaria* (Geoffroy, 1785)**

Cimex testudinarius Geoffroy in Fourcroy, 1785; *Eurygaster maura* var. *notatus* Ferrari, 1874; *Eurygaster sinicus* Walker, 1867; *Eurygaster maura* var. *cinerea* Rey, 1887; *Eurygaster maura* var. *grisescens* Rey, 1888; *Eurygaster maura* var. *rufescens* Oliveira, 1895; *Eurygaster sodalis* Horváth, 1895; *Eurygaster maura* f. *borealis* Péneau, 1911; *Eurygaster sodalis* var. *decorata* Péneau, 1911; *Eurygaster testudinarius* var. *mixta* Cerutti, 1939; *Eurygaster testudinarius* f. *obscuratus* Wagner, 1938; *Eurygaster testudinarius* f. *triguttatus* Wagner, 1938; *Eurygaster testudinarius* f. *tuberculatus* Wagner, 1938; *Eurygaster testudinaria* f. *lurida* Wagner, 1940; *Eurygaster testudinaria* f. *inclusa* Wagner, 1940; *Eurygaster testudinaria* KOna Wagner, 1949; *Eurygaster testudinaria* var. *punctulata* Wagner, 1951; *Eurygaster testudinaria* ab. *flavida* Halászfy, 1959; *Eurygaster testudinaria* ab. *rosea* Halászfy, 1959; *Eurygaster testudinaria* ab. *nigrita* Halászfy, 1959.

Material examined: Çankırı Prov.: Çerkeş, Forest area ahead of Bildircin Plateau, 40°39'10"N, 32°52'4"E, 1800 m, 29.VIII.2013, ♂.

Previous records: Amasya, Ardahan, Artvin, Bartın, Çankırı, Edirne, Erzurum, İstanbul, Kastamonu, Kırklareli, Tekirdağ, Tokat, Zonguldak (Önder et al., 2006; Fent & Aktaş, 2009; Yıldırım et al., 2014a; Küçükbasmacı & Kiyak, 2015).

Subfamily: Odontoscelinae Amyot & Serville, 1843

Genus: *Odontoscelis* Laporte, 1833

Odontoscelis (Odontoscelis) byrrhus* Seidenstücker, 1972Odontoscelis byrrhus* Seidenstücker, 1972.**Material examined:** Çankırı Prov.: Korgun, Ildızım Village entrance, 40°42'31"N, 33°28'3"E, 1031 m, 23.IV.2013, ♀.**Previous records:** Adana, Ankara, Antalya, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Kastamonu, Kayseri, Kırıkkale, Mersin, Nevşehir, Niğde (Önder et al., 2006).***Odontoscelis (Odontoscelis) fuliginosa* (Linnaeus, 1761)***Cimex fuliginosus* Linnaeus, 1761; *Tetyra carbonaria* Zetterstedt, 1819; *Arctocoris fuliginosus* [var.] *aethiops* Germar, 1839; *Odontoscelis fuliginosa* var. *caucasica* Kolenati, 1846; *Odontoscelis fuliginosa* var. *pallasii* Kolenati, 1846; *Odontoscelis fuliginosa* var. *iberica* Kolenati, 1846; *Odontoscelis osellai* Rizzotti Vlach, 1982; *Odontoscelis tamaninii* Rizzotti Vlach, 1982.**Material examined:** Çankırı Prov.: 2. km from Çankırı exit to Yapraklı, 40°35'57"N, 33°37'12"E, 730 m, 23.VII.2013, ♀; Çerkeş, between Akbaş and Aydınlar village, 40°52'44"N, 32°49'4"E, 1489 m, 25.VIII.2013, ♀.**Previous records:** Afyonkarahisar, Ankara, Aydın, Balıkesir, Bartın, Bursa, Denizli, Edirne, Elazığ, Erzurum, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Karaman, Kastamonu, Kırıkkale, Kırşehir, Konya, Zonguldak (Önder et al., 2006; Fent & Aktaş, 2009; Fent & Japoshvili, 2012; Yıldırım et al., 2014a).**Subfamily: Odontotarsinae Mulsant & Rey, 1865****Tribe: Odontotarsini Mulsant & Rey, 1865****Genus: *Odontotarsus* Laporte, 1833*****Odontotarsus rufescens* Fieber, 1861***Odontotarsus grammicus* [var.] *rufescens* Fieber, 1861; *Odontotarsus irroratus* Horváth, 1882; *Odontotarsus rufescens* var. *vittiger* Horváth, 1906; *Odontotarsus purpureolineatus* f. *nigropunctata* Hoberlandt, 1944; *Odontotarsus karatasensis* Hoberlandt, 1956.**Material examined:** Çankırı Prov.: Çerkeş, on the road between Kadiözü- Aliözü villages, 40°49'26"N, 32°57'49"E, 1257 m, 26.VIII.2013, ♀.**Previous records:** Adana, Adıyaman, Amasya, Ankara, Antalya, Artvin, Aydın, Bursa, Denizli, Elazığ, Erzurum, Gaziantep, Gümüşhane, Hatay, İstanbul, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Kars, Kastamonu, Konya, Manisa, Mardin, Mersin, Muğla, Nevşehir (Önder et al., 2006; Matocq et al., 2014; Yıldırım et al., 2014a; Çerçi & Özgen, 2021).**Family STENOCEPHALIDAE Dallas, 1852****Genus: *Dicranocephalus*, Hahn, 1826*****Dicranocephalus albipes* (Fabricius, 1781)***Reduvius albipes* Fabricius, 1781; *Cimex leucopus* Gmelin, 1790; *Dicranomerus neglectus* Herrich-Schaeffer, 1835.**Material examined:** Çankırı Prov.: Çerkeş, between Yıprak-Tohumlar villages, 40°55'1"N, 32°48'34"E, 1153 m, 26.VIII.2013, ♀; Çerkeş, between Kadılar-Dikenli Plateaus, 40°47'35"N, 32°44'35"E, 1449 m, 28.VIII.2013, ♂.**Previous records:** Amasya, Artvin, Bayburt, Çankırı, Çorum, Elazığ, Erzincan, Erzurum, Giresun, Gümüşhane, Iğdır, Kars, Kastamonu, Mersin, Muğla, Sivas, Tokat (Linnavuori, 1965; Dursun, 2009; Yıldırım et al., 2011, 2013a; Matocq et al., 2014; Küçükbasmacı & Kıyak, 2015; Zengin & Dursun, 2019; Akman & Dursun, 2021).**Family TINGIDAE Laporte, 1832****Subfamily: Tinginae Laporte, 1832**

Genus: *Copium* Thunberg, 1822***Copium adumbratum* (Horváth, 1891)**

Eurycera adumbrata Horváth, 1891.

Material examined: Çankırı Prov.: Yapraklı, Yakadere village, 40°41'25"N, 33°48'56"E, 1030 m, 24.VII.2013, ♀.

Previous records: Diyarbakır, Elazığ, Erzincan, Erzurum, Gümüşhane, Mardin, Niğde, Sivas, Samsun, Tokat (Lodos et al., 1984; Önder et al., 2006; Maral et al., 2013; Yıldırım et al., 2013b; Dursun & Fent, 2017; Bolu, 2020; Çerçi & Özgen, 2021).

Genus: *Dictyla*, Stål, 1874***Dictyla echii* (Schrank, 1782)**

Cimex echii Schrank, 1782; *Acanthia echii* Wolff, 1804; *Tingis humuli* (non Fabricius, 1803): Fallén, 1807; *Monanthia (Physatocheila) wolffii* Fieber, 1844; *Monanthia echii* var. *nigricans* Hoberlandt, 1943; *Monanthia echii* var. *rufina* Seidenstücker, 1954.

Material examined: Çankırı Prov.: Korgun, Yukarıçavuş village, 40°42'22"N, 33°38'59"E, 940 m, 21.IV.2013, ♀; Korgun, Ildızım village entry, 40°42'31"N, 33°28'3"E, 1031 m, 23.IV.2013, ♀; Eldivan, Maruf village, 40°38'26"N, 33°25'59"E, 1196 m, 23.IV.2013, 2 ♀♀, 3 ♂♂; Şabanözü, 3. km between Şabanözü-Eldivan road, 40°28'48"N, 33°18'37"E, 1141 m, 24.IV.2013, ♀; Şabanözü, Gümerdiğin, 40°26'40"N, 33°17'2"E, 990 m, 24.IV.2013, ♂.

Previous records: Balıkesir, Bayburt, Diyarbakır, Düzce, Edirne, Elazığ, Erzincan, Erzurum, Giresun, Gümüşhane, Hatay, İstanbul, Kastamonu, Kars, Kastamonu, Kayseri, Kırklareli, Mardin, Rize, Tekirdağ, Tokat (Horváth, 1883; Linnavuori, 1965; Fent & Japoshvili, 2012; Maral et al., 2013; Yıldırım et al. 2013b; Matocq et al., 2014; Dursun & Fent, 2017; Bolu, 2020; Yazıcı, 2022).

***Dictyla nassata nassata* (Puton, 1874)**

Monanthia nassata Puton, 1874; *Monanthia convergens* (non Herrich-Schaeffer, 1835): A. Costa, 1847; *Monanthia putoni* Montandon, 1895; *Monanthia putoni* var. *pulla* Horváth, 1905; *Monanthia comes* Drake, 1948; *Dictyla nassata* f. *heissi* Péricart, 1982.

Material examined: Çankırı Prov.: Kurşunlu, Kurşunlu çıkışı 5. km, Devrez Çayı kenarı, 40°48'53"N, 33°17'28"E, 1126 m, 23.IV.2013, ♀.

Previous records: Edirne, Erzurum, Giresun, Iğdır (Yıldırım et al., 2013b; Dursun & Fent, 2017).

Genus: *Stephanitis* Stål, 1873**Subgenus: *Stephanitis* Stål, 1873*****Stephanitis (Stephanitis) pyri* (Fabricius, 1775)**

Acanthia appendicius, 1775; *Cimex appendiceus* Geoffroy in Fourcroy, 1785; *Tingis marginata* Lamarck, 1816; *Stephanitis pyri* var. *sareptana* Horváth, 1912.

Material examined: Çankırı Prov.: Çerkeş, Aliözü Village exit (towards the main road), 40°49'40"N, 32°56'49"E, 1231 m, 26.VIII.2013, ♂.

Previous records: Adana, Adıyaman, Amasya, Artvin, Bartın, Batman, Diyarbakır, Elazığ, Erzurum, Eskişehir, Gaziantep, Kırklareli, Mardin, Siirt, Şanlıurfa Tekirdağ (Yıldırım et al., 2013b; Aysal & Kıvan, 2018; Maral et al., 2018; Dursun & Fent, 2017; Bolu, 2020).

Genus: *Tingis* Fabricius, 1803**Subgenus: *Neolasiotropis* Wagner, 1961*****Tingis (Neolasiotropis) pilosa* Hummel, 1825**

Tingis pilosa Hummel, 1825; *Monanthia angusticollis* Herrich-Schaeffer, 1836; *Tingis*

(*Tropidocheila*) *kirinana* Drake, 1948.

Material examined: Çankırı Prov.: Eldivan, Maruf villge, 40°38'26"N, 33°25'59"E, 1196 m, 23.IV.2013, ♂; Çerkeş, between Yakuplar and Örenköy, 40°44'44"N, 32°52'25"E, 1301 m, 29.VIII.2013, ♂.

Previous records: Konya (Önder et al., 2006).

Subgenus: *Tingis* Fabricius 1803

Tingis (*Tingis*) *auriculata* (A. Costa, 1847)

Catoplatus auriculatus A. Costa, 1847; *Monanthia* (*Phyllontocheila*) *sinuata* Fieber, 1844; *Monanthia unicolor* Garbiglietti, 1869; *Tingis auriculata* var. *dauci* Horváth, 1905; *Monanthia necopina* Drake, 1919.

Material examined: Çankırı Prov.: Korgun, between Karatekin and Yolkaya village 40°41'30"N, 33°29'20"E, 957 m, 22.IV.2013, ♂; Korgun, Ildızım Village entrance, 40°42'31"N, 33°28'3"E, 1031 m, 23.IV.2013, ♀; Eldivan, Maruf village, 40°38'26"N, 33°25'59"E, 1196 m, 23.IV.2013, 3 ♀♀, 5 ♂♂.

Previous records: Ankara, Artvin, Diyarbakır, Edirne, Elazığ, Erzincan, Erzurum, Giresun, Hatay, Iğdır, Kastamonu, Kırklareli, Sivas, Tokat (Seidenstücker, 1954; Hoberlandt, 1955; Péricart, 1983; Lodos et al., 1984; Maral et al., 2013; Yıldırım et al., 2013b; Matocq et al., 2014; Dursun & Fent, 2017; Bolu, 2020; Yazıcı, 2022).

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